

Quantitative Analysis of Deep Leaf: a Plant Disease Detector on the Smart Edge*

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Abstract—During these years, the Cloud computing paradigm has dominated the scene, representing a widespread solution for a broad variety of systems, however, in the recent period we are witnessing a change in this trend and the computation is starting to approach the data. We usually refer to this phenomenon with the term Edge computing which embodies all the requirements necessary for the creation of Cyber Physical Systems (CPSs). The artificial intelligence also plays a key role in the realization of these systems, through machine learning, in fact they are provided with a new degree of intelligence that allows them to make decisions in an autonomous way. However, CPSs are usually equipped with a hardware that has low energy consumption, but on the other hand, its constrained power and memory make very challenging the execution of complex operations and algorithms (e.g., neural networks) in an effective way. In such a context, compression and quantization techniques can be considered two viable solutions to reduce the memory footprint of neural networks while maximizing their performance on a constrained device. In this paper, we present a quantitative analysis of five different deep learning models, namely: a 32-bit floating point model, a compressed model, and three different types of quantized models. Specifically, to perform this analysis, we realized a real CPS prototype and implemented an AI application, running on a microcontroller of the STM32 family, for the detection of coffee plant diseases through the use of a Quantized Convolutional Neural Network (Q-CNN). In the experimental results, we provide a comparison between these models putting in evidence the differences in terms of accuracy, space utilization, average inference times and energy consumption.

Index Terms—compression, quantization, IoT, Q-CNN, Edge computing, Intelligent Cyber Physical Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era in which the number of devices connected to the Internet is in the order of 20 billion, the management and processing of the data generated from such a huge amount of systems has become a real challenge that is still an open research problem. For many years, the Cloud computing paradigm has been considered the only viable solution, by sending the data to remote servers providing large storage and high power processing services accessible by any device with internet communications capabilities [].

* This work was done while Fabrizio De Vita was visiting Missouri University of Science and Technology. This work is part of the H2020-ECSEL-2017-2-RIA-two-stage funded project AFarCloud, Aggregate FARMing in the CLOUD

However, with the advancement of ICT technology and the Internet of Things (IoT) widespreading, a new type of systems has emerged that has brought with it a new set of requirements that the Cloud is usually unable to meet. Such systems work both as sensors and actuators and are usually provided with two interfaces that enable them to interact with each other and with the physical world surrounding them; in this sense, because of their double “nature” they are called Cyber Physical Systems (CPSs) [1]. The use of these devices has a huge impact on our lives and totally changed the way we interact with the physical world. The market related to this area has literally exploded, and the economic potential of CPS applications as well as the number of scenarios where this technology can be exploited increases day by day. Moreover, we firmly believe that artificial intelligence (AI) will play a key role in this sector. Thanks to machine learning, in fact, we are able to add a new degree of intelligence to these systems, which are typically called Intelligent Cyber Physical Systems (ICPSs), that allow them to make autonomous decisions depending on the context [2].

In this sense, if on the one hand the Cloud computing paradigm has been very useful for the diffusion of the CPS technology, on the other it exposes several limitations especially in terms of latency and security. In such a context, in fact, we are observing a shift of the computation from the internet to the location where the data is collected. We usually refer to this phenomenon with the term Edge computing to indicate a paradigm in which the data is processed on a device which is “close” to it [3]. Of course, moving the computation from the Cloud to the Edge comes with a new set of challenges which are mainly related to the constrained hardware available on these devices. Specifically, these systems are designed to be energy efficient because of their always-on nature that allows them to continuously “listen” the surrounding environment, however, such a feature can be obtained by only limiting the computing power of the device. In this sense, the execution of complex operations or algorithms (i.e., neural networks models) can be quite challenging. Recently, several techniques have been proposed to solve this kind of problem and involve the *compression* or the *quantization* of the model with the aim to be run on a constrained hardware while maintaining its performance [4].

In this paper, we present a quantitative analysis in terms

of accuracy, inference time, space utilization, and energy consumption of five different deep learning models, namely a 32-bit floating point model, a compressed model, a model quantized using Tensor Flow Lite (TFLite) converter, a model quantized using an integer representation, and another one using a fixed point (i.e., Q-format or Qm,n) representation. In particular, to perform the above analysis we designed a working prototype of an ICPS, on top of which we implemented an AI application running on a microcontroller of the STM32 family, for the detection of coffee plant diseases through the use of a Quantized Convolutional Neural Network (Q-CNN).

The contributions are the following. *i.)* We realize a working ICPS for the coffee plant disease detection. *ii.)* We deploy a Q-CNN on a microcontroller belonging to the STM32 family, using the *X-CUBE-AI* tool provided by STMicroelectronics. *iii.)* We provide an extensive quantitative analysis which compares five different deep learning models.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related works and highlights the differences with our work. Section III describes the adopted hardware and the tools used to execute the compression and quantization processes. Section IV provides a detailed description of the AI application we realized to perform the quantitative analysis. Section V provides the experimental results from testing the above mentioned five deep learning models. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper with directions about the future works.

II. RELATED WORKS

The use of quantization techniques is not new in the literature. The survey in [5] discussed the current challenges and trends related to the use of a Quantized Neural Network (QNN). This section reviews existing works and articulates the differences with our proposed work.

At a time in which the computation is getting closer to the user, authors in [6] put in evidence that the use of quantization techniques on neural networks represents an enabling technology for the deployment of energy efficient AI powered applications on the Edge.

The authors in [7] propose a framework based on the pruning technique to compress and accelerate CNN models during both the training and inference processes. The experimental results show very good performance both in terms of accuracy and inference times, however, compression techniques are sometimes not sufficient to obtain a model which can be executed on a microcontroller due to its low amount of RAM and flash available. In this sense, our work proposes a quantitative analysis of differences between a compressed model and a quantized one putting in evidence its advantages both in terms of inference times and energy consumption.

Authors in [8] propose a Keyword Spotting Systems (KWS) for a speech recognition application which is run on a Cortex-M7 based STM32F746G-disco development board. Due to the board constrained hardware, in this work, the authors adopted a quantization technique based on ARM CMSIS-NN kernels [4] to reduce the memory footprint of the proposed Deep Neural Network (DNN) models while improving the energy

efficiency. Unlike our approach, this work provides only a comparison in terms of accuracy between several DNN models and their corresponding quantized version.

Authors in [9] present an embedded application for acoustic event detection based on compact recurrent neural networks. Also in this case, the authors adopted a fixed point 8-bit quantization using the ARM CMSIS-NN framework. In this work, we used the STMicroelectronics *X-CUBE-AI* tool (instead of the CMSIS-NN) to deploy a quantized deep neural network directly into a microcontroller. Such a software (that will be described in the next section), allows to directly transfer a pre-trained float model into an ST board, providing also a set of functionalities to validate and test the converted model.

III. ST ENVIRONMENT & MODEL CONVERSION TECHNIQUES

In this section, we describe the materials used in our experiments. These are both software and hardware, made available by STMicroelectronics.

A. STM32 Discovery board

The STM32F746GDISCOVERY Discovery kit is a complete demonstration and development platform for STMicroelectronics Arm® Cortex®-M7 core-based STM32F746NG microcontroller. It includes 1 Mbyte of Flash memory and 340 Kbytes of RAM, in BGA216 package. The board includes a set of complete peripherals, in order to develop user applications, before the final porting on custom boards. The Discovery kit enables a wide diversity of applications, taking benefit from audio, multi-sensor support, AI, graphics, security, video and high-speed connectivity features. Fig. 1 shows the front and back sides of the board.

Fig. 1: STM32F746G-disco board.

The Discovery kit uses the STM32F746NG microcontroller features, in order to enable the included peripherals in the board, i.e., a 4.3" RGB 480×272 color LCD-TFT with capacitive touch screen, two ST-MEMS digital microphones, 128-Mbit Quad-SPI Flash memory, 128-Mbit SDRAM (64 Mbits accessible), two user and reset push-buttons. It also includes connectors to expand the board capabilities, i.e.: Camera, microSD™ card, Audio line in and line out jack, 2×USB with Micro-AB, ARDUINO Uno V3 expansion connectors.

The on-board ST-Link/V2-1 programmer enables virtual COM port, mass storage and debug port functions. Regarding the power supply, the board can be powered from 3.6 to 12 volts, thus facilitating its integration into existing circuitry.

B. X-CUBE-AI

The STM32F746NG microcontroller and the whole Discovery kit are configurable from the STM32CubeMX tool. It allows to enable and configure the microcontroller features in a quick and user friendly way. The STM32CubeMX tool also allows to manage an expansion package, called X-CUBE-AI [10]. It has the capability to automatically convert a pre-trained neural network, and then integrating an optimized library into the user's project. The expansion package also provides some metrics to validate the neural network model generated on both PCs and STM32 devices, without having to develop any ad-hoc C code. X-CUBE-AI significantly extends the feature-set of the STM32CubeMX tool by enabling it to import any artificial neural network trained with many of the most popular libraries available for free today, such as Keras, TensorFlow Lite, ONNX, Caffe, Lasagne, or ConvnetJS. This tool also supports 8-bit quantization of the Keras models and Tensorflow Lite quantized networks. It also allows to import networks larger than the STM32 microcontroller resources, storing the weights on external Flash memory, and the activation buffers on external RAM modules. One of the most challenging aspects of the integration of a neural network into an embedded system is related to memory occupancy. If the model can fit on the embedded memory of a processor, huge energy savings can be achieved, and hence this motivates developing a fully embedded memory implementation of CNN. For this reason, STM32Cube.AI, in addition to quantization, offers also a weights compression strategy, that can be exploited to make a large model to fit in the limited STM32 MCU memory. More details on both compression and quantization techniques, exploited by X-CUBE-AI, will be disclosed in the two successive sections.

C. Compression technique

X-CUBE-AI gives the user the opportunity of compressing weights, in case a network cannot fit in the selected MCU, due to higher flash requirements. The implemented weights and biases compression (target-factor: none, x4, x8) is only applicable on dense layers, and this is motivated by the fact that most of the weights of a neural network are in the fully connected layers. Each dense layer is taken into account individually and all the weights contained in it are clustered using the k-means algorithm, where the number of centroids is defined as a function of the compression factor we want to achieve. Assuming that the uncompressed weights are represented in single precision floating point, the number of centroids, given a certain target-factor, can be calculated as follows:

$$n_{centroids} = 2^{\frac{32}{\text{target-factor}}} \quad (1)$$

D. Quantization techniques

X-CUBE-AI offers the capability to import, besides a native TensorFlow Lite quantized model, a Keras-based quantized model, opportunely reshaped by the Command Line Interface (console level) provided by X-CUBE-AI. When a quantized model is loaded, the code generator quantizes weights and bias, and associated activations from floating point to 8-bit precision. These are mapped on the optimized and specialized C implementation for the supported kernels. The objective of this technique is to reduce the model size while also improving the CPU and hardware accelerator latency (including power consumption aspects) with little degradation in model accuracy. A TensorFlow Lite model is a self-contained file able to handle floating-point or/and quantized model (weight/bias are already converted). This is not the case for Keras models: Keras h5 file does not provide a support to handle quantized params or meta information. For this reason, a reshaped Keras model file (h5*) and a proprietary tensor format configuration file (json file) are requested by the tool. For the Keras-based model, thanks to the tensor format configuration file, the code generator is able to quantize (or to convert) the weights/bias and associated activations from floating-point to integer precision. To generate the reshaped Keras model file and associated tensor format configuration file, the stm32ai application integrates a complete Keras post-training quantization process (quantize command). The Keras post-training quantization process goes through a flow, which is depicted in Fig. 2. In particular, the quantization flows includes the

Fig. 2: Quantization steps.

following steps: *i.*) Reshape the model. *ii.*) Quantize the model. *iii.*) Predict with emulated quantized model. More details on this process can be found at [11]. By default, X-CUBE-AI supports the standard 32-bit float arithmetic for the most imported models. For the quantized models, integer arithmetic or less-precision arithmetic, no standard is defined. X-CUBE-AI supports two integer-base arithmetic: Qm,n and Integer. Qm,n arithmetic is a signed fixed-point number format (two's complement) where the number of fractional bits n and the number of integer bits m are specified with a constant and fixed resolution. For the integer arithmetic, each real number r is represented in function of the quantized value q, a scale factor (arbitrary positive real number) and a zero_point parameters.

IV. AI APPLICATION

Aspects related to the plant disease detection are gaining a lot of interest in the smart agriculture sector. Being able to perform an initial analysis on plants suspected of being affected by a disease, can be very important to save them, but above all to prevent the spread of epidemics on the plantations. In such a context, where the assumption to have a constant internet connection can not be always satisfied, and the number of plants to analyze can be very large, the use of the Cloud paradigm would require too much time for the detection. For all these reasons, there is the necessity to realize a system capable to perform an on-site early analysis of plants health condition to support the human operator during the diagnosis process.

Fig. 3: ICPS prototype containing STM32F746G-disco.

However, the deployment of applications on the Edge constrained devices could be difficult, especially if we consider AI powered applications which require a lot of computing power. In this sense, the challenge consists in the deployment of a software that can be run on the Edge while maintaining its performance. As already explained in Section III, there are different techniques that can be adopted to reduce the complexity of an application such that it can be run on a constrained device, but depending on the available hardware and on the application context sometimes an approach could be preferred among the others. This is in particular the aim of our work, which is to provide a broad quantitative analysis highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of each approach.

In this section, we describe the AI application we implemented which is part of an ICPS we realized. Specifically, the application is able to detect the main biotic diseases that typically affect the coffee trees by analyzing the pictures of their leaves. Fig. 3 depicts the prototype we created consisting of an STM32F746G-disco board (already described in Section III) connected to an STM32F4DIS-CAM module, both embedded in a polymethylmethacrylate box equipped with some LEDs which are used to light the coffee leaf while the camera module takes the picture.

A. Dataset description

The dataset we adopted for our application is made up of pictures of healthy and diseased coffee leaves which are affected by the main biotic stresses of the coffee tree. Fig. 4

shows the healthy (Fig. 4a) and diseased leaves; specifically, the diseases took into consideration are: miner (Fig. 4b), brown leaf spot (generically called “phoma”) (Fig. 4c) and rust (Fig. 4d). From the original dataset¹ we extracted 274 leaves’ images belonging to the healthy class, 323 leaves images belonging to the miner class, 343 leaves images belonging to the phoma class and 350 leaves images belonging to the rust class, for a total of 1290 images.

All images were 512x256 pixels, with a ratio of 2:1. However the camera module attached to the board takes pictures with a squared ratio, for this reason, we resized all the images into a square format of 224x224 pixels (ratio 1:1) avoiding stretching and cropping.

At this step, the images were divided into training, validation and test datasets by using the ratio 80%, 10%, and 10% respectively. However, after this division, the total number of samples for the training and validation datasets was too low (about 1021 and 134 samples respectively). To overcome this issue, that would have caused an overfitting of our model, we decided to apply the data augmentation technique to our images. Such a technique allows to generate new instances of data from the existing one through the application of different random transformations i.e., movements, rotations, flips, zooms, and skews [12]. In particular, the use of the data augmentation has a double advantage: it allows to increase the number of training samples, thus making the model more robust.

Another problem we faced, was related to the quality of the camera module. Such a module has a resolution lower than a smartphone camera so its pictures result noisy and with a lower quality if compared to the ones available in the dataset. For this reason, to force the model to be more tolerant to low lighting conditions and noise, a vignette effect was added on half of the images both on training and validation datasets. Moreover, different kinds of noises were randomly added. Specifically, for each image in the training and validation datasets, it was randomly chosen if apply a gaussian noise, a Poisson noise, a sparkle noise or to maintain the image without noise. Fig. 5 shows two examples of the data augmentation process.

At the end of the data augmentation operations, we reached a total of 23462 images for the training dataset and 3057 images for the validation one. For a better visualization, Table I summarizes the number of samples for each set (i.e., training, validation, and test) after the data augmentation process.

TABLE I: Number of samples for training, validation, and test sets after the data augmentation process.

Class	Training	Validation	Test	Total images
Healthy	5055	621	27	5703
Miner	5931	735	32	6698
Phoma	6297	781	34	7112
Rust	6179	920	40	7139
Total	23462	3057	133	26652

¹<https://drive.google.com/file/d/15YHebAGrx1Vh8-naave-R5o3Uo70jsm/view>

Fig. 4: Leaves belonging to all different classes.

(a) Augmented image healthy (b) Augmented image miner

Fig. 5: Augmented images example.

B. CNN description

The task of detecting plant diseases has been tackled as a supervised multiclass classification problem with a number of classes equal to 4 (i.e., healthy, miner, phoma, and rust).

The machine learning technique we used to realize the classifier is an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) belonging to the category of the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). These models are particular DNNs generally used for visual recognition and classification tasks which, differently from classical computer vision systems, automatically learn how to extract the features which allow the classification process.

Fig. 6: Complete structure of the CNN.

Fig. 6 depicts the complete structure of the CNN through which it is possible to analyze the layer characteristics. From

a topological point of view, a CNN is structured into two parts. The first part consisting of the convolutional and the max-pooling layers is responsible for the *feature extraction* process, through which the network is able to learn the internal structure of the input images (i.e., lines, edges, shapes, etc.). The second part of the CNN is the one which makes the actual classification (or detection in this case). It is usually composed by a sequence of fully connected layers whose take as input a vector containing the features extracted by the network at the previous stage, and are terminated by a softmax layer which outputs the most probable class associated to the input image provided to the CNN. Analyzing Fig. 6, it is possible to observe these 2 distinct parts in our CNN. The feature extraction part starts from the input layer and contains all the layers until the last convolutional one (i.e., the 7). The classification part instead contains the fully connected layers until the output one.

Starting from the input layer 1, it is possible to examine its size, which corresponds to $224 \times 224 \times 3$ because the network takes in input 224×224 pixels RGB images.

The layer 2, following the input one, is a convolutional layer with 32 filters with a map size 8×8 and a stride 4×4 . Such a layer performs the convolution operation between the filter and the input image and the output is next passed through a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function. In particular, we choose to use the ReLU activation function for each layer of our CNN, because as known by the literature [13], it allows to speed up the training phase without having significant differences in the accuracy with respect to the other activation functions like the *sigmoid* or the *hyperbolic tangent*.

After the first convolutional layer, we added a pooling layer 3 with a map size and a stride 2×2 , whose purpose is to reduce the feature map size derived from the previous layer and to make the model more invariant to small translations of the input. In particular, every pooling layer adopted in our topology is a *max-pooling* layer whose functioning consists in extracting the maximum value for each portion of the selected feature map.

A group of two convolutional layers follows the first max-pooling one, namely: layer 4 with 64 filters with a map size 3×3 and a stride 2×2 , and layer 5 with 128 filters with a map size 3×3 and a stride 1×1 . Layer 6 is the last max-pooling.

Like the previous pooling it has a map size and a stride 2×2 , and it is inserted between the two above mentioned layers and before the last convolutional layer 7, which has 64 filters with a map size 3×3 and a stride 1×1 .

The last convolutional layer is then followed by a *flatten* layer which transforms a multidimensional matrix into a one-dimensional vector to be used as input for a fully connected layer with which begins the classifier network part.

The first fully connected layer 8 contains 128 neurons completely connected to the output of the flatten layer. Just like we did for the convolutional layers, also in this case, we used the ReLU as activation function.

Moreover, after this fully connected layer, a dropout layer with a probability drop rate of 0.2 is used as a regularization technique to prevent the network overfitting. In particular, only during the training phase, the dropout layer at each iteration randomly removes the 20% of neurons from layer 8. It is proven by the literature [14] that the use of this technique makes the system more stable and robust to generalization.

In the same way, another fully connected layer 9 with 32 neurons and a dropout layer with a 0.5 rate follow the first fully connected one.

Finally, for the output layer 10, we used a softmax function made up of 4 output neurons where each one represents one of the classes we want to classify (i.e., healthy, miner, phoma, and rust).

We labeled our data by using a one-hot encoding labeling, so in our model compiling step, we used the *categorical_crossentropy* as loss function which particularly fitting for the classification tasks.

With respect to the optimizer, we opted for the *Stochastic Gradient Descent* (SGD) optimizer, for which we set a learning rate of 0.01 that allows to take the advantages of the SGD like the speed up in finding a minimum and the high variance of the parameters which bring to the possibility of discovering different local minima.

With the aim of avoiding overfitting and underfitting that could be caused by choosing an incorrect number of training epochs, we adopted the *early stopping* technique. Specifically, it monitors the loss on the validation dataset and the overall model accuracy saving each time the model which performed best. The training process is automatically stopped if after 30 consecutive epochs (i.e., the “patience” term we set for our model) the model is not able to improve the loss. Thanks to this technique, it is possible to avoid possible networks overtraining and obtain the model which performed best during the training both in terms of accuracy and validation loss.

For a better visualization, Table II summarizes the model parameters used in the designing process of the CNN.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section provides a quantitative analysis derived from the comparison of 5 different models of the above plant disease detection application we implemented. In particular, we compared the original float 32-bit model, the compressed version, the quantized model using TFLite converter, the quantized one

TABLE II: Convolutional Neural Network parameters.

CNN model architecture	
<i>No. of layers</i>	10
<i>Activation function</i>	<i>ReLU</i>
<i>Pooling method</i>	<i>Max-pooling</i>
<i>Dropout rate</i>	[0.5, 0.2]
<i>Learning rate</i>	0.01
<i>Patience</i>	30
<i>Max training epochs</i>	150
<i>Optimizer</i>	<i>SGD</i>

using the Qm,n format, and the quantized version using the integer format. Specifically, for each model we measured their performance in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, then, we deeply analyzed the compressed and quantized models for which we provide a comparison also in terms of flash and RAM utilization, average inference times, and average energy consumption. Each result we show in this section has been obtained considering the STM32F746G-disco board as testbed, the X-CUBE-AI tool for the deployment of the models on the microcontroller, and the same test dataset already described in Table I.

With respect to the first model (i.e., the 32-bits float) we designed, it reached a 96.24% of accuracy on the test dataset. Moreover, to have a complete vision of the results reached by the algorithm, we computed the confusion matrix (shown in Fig. 7) through which is possible to measure the performance of the deep learning model by extracting useful indexes like *precision*, *recall*, and F_1 -*score*.

Fig. 7: Confusion matrix of the classifier.

TABLE III: Precision, recall and F_1 -score of the classifier.

Class	Precision	Recall	F_1 -score	Support
Health	0.96	1.00	0.98	27
Miner	0.94	0.94	0.94	32
Phoma	1.00	0.94	0.97	34
Rust	0.95	0.97	0.96	40

The values of precision, recall and F_1 -score obtained for the model are reported in the Table III. In particular, the model has been able to get very high values for each one of the indexes

with values ranging from 0.95 to 1.0, thus demonstrating its generalization capabilities.

The *Keras* model was exported in a *.h5 file which occupies 2.1 Mbytes on the disk. As described in Section III-A, the STM32F746G-disco board is equipped with 1 Mbyte of flash memory which means that the above mentioned model can not be run natively on the microcontroller. In this sense, to deploy our model into the board we used the techniques of compression and quantization described in Section III.

We started by compressing the model using a compression factor equal to 8, this allowed us to reduce the model flash and RAM occupation to 729.49 Kbytes and 619.78 Kbytes respectively. The choice to not use a compression factor of 4 derives from the fact that the obtained results for this model were perfectly comparable, but with a larger amount of flash required due to lower compression factor. However, even after this procedure the model was still too large to be fit on the microcontroller. In fact, if on the hand with the compression technique we were able to sufficiently reduce the amount of flash, on the other the RAM required was still too high as the board is provided with just 340 Kbytes. To overcome this issue, we configured the STM32F746G-disco in order to provide the access to the external SDRAM which resulted to be fundamental to store and run the compressed model.

Just like we did for the float model, also in this case, we evaluated the performance of the compressed model by computing the confusion matrix and extracting its metrics. The results obtained on the test dataset are the same we reported in Fig. 7. In this sense, since the precision, recall and consequently the F_1 -score definitions depend on the confusion matrix values, also these quantities coincide with the values we reported in Table III.

With respect to inference time, by testing the model on the test dataset, each inference averagely lasted 1022.81 ms with an average of 220927803 CPU cycles and 31593500 of *Multiply-and-ACCumulate* (MACC) operations considering a CPU clock of 216 MHz. In such a context, an useful metric is represented by the cycles/MACC ratio which highlights the efficiency of the C-model implementation (i.e., the smaller this ratio the more efficient the implementation), that in this case, for the compressed model is equal to 6.99.

The STM32CubeMX software also allows to estimate the average energy consumption of a board depending on its setup. In particular, by properly setting the board configuration in terms of the clock frequency and active peripherals, it possible to estimate the average consumption in terms of current. According to the documentation provided by STMicroelectronics, the peripherals enabled by our application are the following: the Digital CaMera Interface (DCMI) needed to communicate with the camera module, the Direct Memory Access (DMA) and the Direct Memory Access 2D (DMA2D) for the image manipulation, the LCD-TFT Display Controller (LTDC) to control the display and a timer (TM1).

Considering the compressed model, in this specific case it has been necessary also to enable the external SDRAM and the Quad Serial Peripheral Interface (QSPI) for the commu-

nication with this component. In such a context, the average absorbed current by the board per millisecond (\bar{i}) was equal to 305.67 mA, in this sense, considering a supply voltage (V_{dd}) equal to 3.3 V and an average inference time (\bar{t}) of 1022.81 ms, it is possible to compute the average energy consumption (\bar{E}) for each inference as follows:

$$\bar{E} = \bar{i} \cdot V_{dd} \cdot \bar{t} \quad (2)$$

According to Eq. 2 the compressed model has average energy consumption for each inference equal to 1031.72 mJ.

The third model we analyze has been obtained by adopting a quantization technique through the use of the TFLite converter that allowed to reduce the flash occupation to 251.79 Kbytes and the RAM to 33.25 Kbytes, thus making the size much smaller than the one obtained through the compression operation and allowing to run the model without using the external SDRAM. Also in this case, the obtained confusion matrix coincided with the ones computed for the float and compressed models. Such a result has been very significant since we were able to deploy a model which was on the one hand small and on the other had the same performance in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F_1 -score.

Considering the inference time, in this case each inference took an average of 364.44 ms (about a quarter if compared with the compressed model) with an average number of 78719324 CPU cycles and requiring 31469676 of MACC operations. Also in terms of cycles/MACC, we obtained very good results with a value of 2.50 which is about 3 times lower than the one obtained by the compressed model.

With respect to the power consumption the TFLite model resulted very energy efficient, in this case in fact it was not necessary to enable the QSPI and SDRAM peripherals which both have a huge impact on the absorbed current. With this new configuration and assuming the same V_{dd} , the average absorbed current per millisecond \bar{i} was equal to 135.66 mA and according to Eq. 2 the average energy consumption for each inference was 163.15 mJ (about 6.5 times less than the compressed model).

The quantization using the Qm,n representation format is one of the techniques directly provided by the X-CUBE-AI tool. Such a quantization generated a model occupying 250.44 KBytes on flash and 32.35 KBytes on RAM which allowed to run it without the need of the SDRAM. In terms of performance this model resulted to be first with a reduced value of accuracy equal to 94.73%. Such a result is due to the Qm,n representation format that cause a higher loss of information during the DNN conversion (if compared with the other quantization schemes) with a consequent degradation of the performance.

Fig. 8 depicts the confusion matrix for the Qm,n quantized model. If compared with the one showed in Fig. 7, the new model misclassified 2 instances of the *miner* class with a consequent reduction of the precision, recall, and F_1 -score (showed in Table IV), which are still very good with values that range between 0.93 and 1.0.

Fig. 8: Confusion matrix of the classifier for Qm,n quantized model.

TABLE IV: Precision, recall and F₁-score of the classifier for Qm,n quantized model.

Class	Precision	Recall	F ₁ -score	Support
Health	0.93	1.00	0.96	27
Miner	0.93	0.88	0.90	32
Phoma	1.00	0.94	0.97	34
Rust	0.93	0.95	0.97	40

With regards to the inference time, in this case we registered an average value of 299.60 ms with an average number of 64712955 CPU cycles, 31593508 MACC operations and a cycles/MACC ratio of 2.05 which resulted to be lowest values among the 5 models compared in this quantitative analysis.

Considering the same hardware configurations we described for the TFLite quantized model, so assuming an expected average consumption equal to 135.66 mA and a V_{dd} value equal to 3.3 V, in a context in which the inferences lasted on average 299.60 ms, the average energy consumption for each inference is equal to 134.12 mJ which is again the lowest value of energy consumption.

The final model we analyze has been obtained using again the the X-CUBE-AI tool selecting in this case the a quantization technique with an integer representation format. Using this type of quantization, we obtained a model which occupied 251.79 KBytes on flash and 32.60 KBytes on RAM which are both sufficient small to run the model without the SDRAM just like the other two quantized models. In such a context, the model obtained maintained the same accuracy and the same confusion matrix of the original float model.

In terms of inference time the model performed each inference on the test dataset with an average of 360.41 ms with an average number of 77848890 CPU cycles and 31469668 MACC operations, and a cycles/MACC ratio equal to 2.47.

Finally, assuming again the same hardware configuration described for both the TFLite and the Qm,n quantized models, the model reported an average energy consumption for each inference equal to 161.34 mJ.

For a better visualization Table V shows all the results obtained for each model described above where the “-” symbol along the the row of the float model indicates a non available

value due to the impossibility to directly run on the board the original model.

A. Lessons learned

Taking a closer look to Table V and Fig. 9, it is possible to extract interesting insights on the two techniques explained above. In general, we can say that the compression technique produces a model that reaches the largest values in terms of flash and RAM occupation, inference time, cycles/MACC. In our application context, even if the model maintained the same accuracy, precision, recall, and F₁-score of the original float one, its use is discouraged due the need of the SDRAM module which has very high energy consumption.

On the contrary, the quantized models using the TFLite converter and the X-CUBE-AI tool obtained very good results heavily reducing the flash and RAM occupation. Specifically, the TFLite quantized model and the quantized one using the integer format reached the same performance of the original model, but with lower values of inference time, and energy consumption if compared to the compressed model. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the quantization techniques over the compression ones when working with DNNs with a large number of layers like our case. However, the performance of the quantization is heavily influenced by the type of the representation format and the tuning of the parameters (i.e., number of bits, quantization steps, number of intervals, etc.). In this sense, they require the implementation of efficient algorithms which can take a lot of time to find the best set of quantization parameters. In such a context, the X-CUBE-AI tool took about 5 hours to quantize our model, and in general the time required increases with the complexity of the network.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we designed an ICPS on top which we implemented an AI application for the plant disease detection on coffee leaves. Specifically, the application has been deployed on an STM32F746G-disco board powered by a microcontroller of the STM32 family, through the X-CUBE-AI tool developed by STMicroelectronics. Such a tool provides two different techniques (i.e., compression and quantization) to reduce the memory footprint of a deep learning model while maximizing its performance on a constrained hardware.

This work produced a quantitative analysis of 5 different models for which we measured the performance in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F₁-score with a particular focus on comparing flash an RAM space occupation, average inference time and energy consumption. For our application context, the compression technique resulted to be inefficient as it maintained the accuracy of the original float model, but with very large flash and and RAM occupations and energy consumption; in the Edge context, where the devices are battery driven such a condition can not be accepted. On the one hand, the quantized models performed very well on the board, in this sense the results obtained demonstrated that this technique outperforms the compression in every index we

TABLE V: Measurement on models.

Model	Flash (KB)	RAM (KB)	AVG Inf. Time (ms)	Accuracy	AVG Energy Cons. (mJ)	Cycles/MACC
Float	-	-	-	0.96	-	-
Compressed	729.49	619.78	1022.81	0.96	1031.72	6.99
Quantized TFLite	251.79	33.25	364.44	0.96	163.15	2.50
Quantized Qm,n Format	250.44	32.35	299.60	0.94	134.12	2.05
Quantized Integer Format	251.79	32.60	360.41	0.96	161.34	2.47

Fig. 9: Histogram plot that compares the compressed and quantized models.

measured, on the other they require a careful selection and tuning of the quantization parameters that can take a lot of time according to the model complexity.

Future works will be devoted to the improvement of the application performance in order to detect more and multiple diseases and to the analysis of more sophisticated compression and quantization techniques.

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